

A REALISTIC 3-D TEXTILE GEOMETRIC MODEL

E. Zhou,^{1,2} D. Mollenhauer,¹ and E. Iarve^{1,2}

¹Air Force Research Laboratory, 2941 Hobson Way, WPAFB, OH45433, USA

²University of Dayton Research Institute, 300 College Park, Dayton, OH45469, USA

E-mail: eric.zhou@wpafb.af.mil

SUMMARY

A 3-D textile geometric model was developed to predict the realistic yarn geometry based on the fiber distribution by simulating textile composite processes, such as weaving, braiding, and vacuum bagging. A robust multi-cluster method was developed to subdivide each yarn into multiple parametric volumes for mesh generation.

Keywords: 3-D textile composite, Micro-geometry, Textile modeling, Numerical simulation, Deformation

ABSTRACT

Textile composites are widely used in automotive, naval, and aerospace industries. The variation of the topology of the textile structure will affect the performance of the composite. The yarn micro-geometry is determined by 1) the textile process, such as weaving, braiding, etc. and 2) the composite forming process, such as vacuum bagging, resin transfer molding, etc. In this paper, we present a method to predict fiber distribution by simulating the textile deformation under the textile process and the vacuum bagging process. The fiber-level distribution is then transformed into the yarn-based description by the yarn-surface smoothing method. Further, each yarn was subdivided into multiple parametric volumes for the three-dimensional stress analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Textile composites are widely used in automotive, naval, and aerospace industries. The tailoring of textile reinforcement structures for advanced composites has mainly focused on achieving high modulus and high strength. However, the progressive damage failure is one of the most common failures in their applications and it is dependent upon textile fabric geometry. The variation of the topology of the textile structure could affect the performance of the composite. Cox and Flanagan reported that irregularity of yarn geometry and undulation has a modest effect on the average elastic module but a strong effect on the strength [1]. The strength, notch sensitivity, and delaminating resistance all require detailed modeling of yarn geometry. To optimize an accurate damage prediction method, we should consider the realistic yarn geometry instead of the idealized one. The study of detailed yarn topology is an effective way to optimize the design of textile reinforcement. The detailed textile geometry is determined by textile processes, forming processes, and ultimately the resin transfer molding (RTM) process. Since a yarn consists of a bundle of fibers, the distribution of fibers determines the yarn geometry. For each fiber, its position and undulation are the results of balanced forces

applied on the fiber, such as fiber tension, inter-fiber compression, inter-fiber friction, and external compacting force. Three main approaches have been applied for representing the yarn geometry:

a) Idealized yarn architecture approximation. It has been used by many researchers. It can predict mechanical properties of a textile composite with a certain degree of accuracy. However, it may not be suitable for progressive damage analysis, since the initiation and growth of a crack always depends on the local detailed yarn geometry. The general application of this method is limited in structural analysis. It treats the structural component as a homogeneous material [2-5].

b) The realistic yarn geometry approach. It is a relatively new technology. Lomov, et al. measured yarn geometry in the free state and its behavior in the loading state, and then employed an algorithm of conformal mapping to predict fiber distribution in a textile composite. The assumption of constant cross section leads to the yarn interpenetration. To solve this problem, yarn is twisted to reduce the intersection [6]. Zhou and Wang [7] developed a multi-chain digital element model to predict distribution of fibers during the textile process. This method calculated all individual fibers' positions subject to loads by solving the equilibrium equations. This approach leads to only small interpenetration, which may occur in the process of smoothing the digital chain boundaries into yarn boundaries. However, the effects of the composite forming process on the fabric geometry have not been investigated yet.

c) The third approach is 3-D digital image reconstruction. This approach determines the description of textile architecture based on image reconstruction techniques. The images from an optical microscope or other sources can be segmented into objective constituents and reconstructed into 3-D geometries [8,9]. Since images are scanned from the experiment directly, the geometry generated based on these images presents a real description of the textile architecture. In this paper, we focus on how to predict the textile geometry with the applied compacting force.

Multi-chain Digital Element

In 2000, Sun and Wang developed a concept of the digital element to predict the yarn path by simulating the textile processing [10]. In their approach, each yarn was modeled as a frictionless pin-connected rod element, which is defined as a “digital element” (Figure 1.a). However, the method can only obtain the approximate yarn path not the yarn geometry, because the yarn was modeled as a rod with rigid properties in the transverse direction. Since then, Zhou and Wang continued to work on the yarn geometry issue by defining each yarn as an assembly of multiple digital chains, called “multi-chain digital element” [7]. Each digital chain is represented as a bundle of fibers instead of a yarn. Therefore, by examining the final distribution of these chains, one can predict the realistic yarn geometry. In reality, a yarn consists of thousands of discrete fibers. The bonding force between fibers in the yarn is very weak compared with the fiber's transverse rigidity. Therefore, when the load is applied on the yarn, the individual fiber should be forced to move out of its original position instead of being deformed in the transverse direction, as shown in Figure 1.b. The following assumptions were made:

1) Only fiber tensile deformation in the axial direction was considered;

- 2) No deformation exists in the fiber transverse direction;
- 3) Fiber curvature is achieved by bending the joint between the two neighboring elements; and
- 4) The final yarn geometry is determined by the fiber's distributions at each cross section.

The stiffness matrix of the multi-chain digital element is similar to the 3-D truss element with extra constant stiffness at each joint pin. The contact stiffness was carefully redefined after each relaxation step to mimic the entangled fibers. Physically, a yarn is composed of hundreds or thousands of fibers. A direct representation of each fiber as a digital chain is not feasible. The following steps are taken to increase the efficiency of the modeling.

- 1) A far smaller amount of digital chains is used here to represent individual yarn, while each chain represents a bundle of real fibers. From comparison of simulations and experimental observations, the authors found that the 19 digital-chain yarn model is sufficient in numerical simulation to predict micro-geometries [11].
- 2) In the multi-chain digital element approach, a new static relaxation method has replaced the step-by-step textile process method in the original digital element approach. Initial yarn architecture is established based upon known fabric information from literature, measurement, and database. The yarns are discretized into multiple digital chains. The nonequilibrium force induced to each node is calculated and then relaxed. Compared to the step-by-step textile method, less than 10% computer resource is required to generate the same fabric [11].

The stiffness of the digital element can be written as:

$$[K] = \frac{EA}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta & 0 & 0 & -\Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Delta & 0 & 0 & -\Delta \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\Delta & 0 & 0 & \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\Delta & 0 & 0 & \Delta \end{bmatrix}$$

where E is the modulus of the yarn, L is the length of the digital element and A is the area of the cross section. Δ is a small perturbation for the support stiffness, which is necessary to be added to the element stiffness matrix to avoid singularity. Because of the assumption that the digital element can only support the tension, the global stiffness matrix may become singular if any two neighboring digital elements are aligned as a straight line. The digital element's length/diameter ratio is recommended as smaller than 0.75. The contact stiffness matrix can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} k_n & 0 & 0 & -k_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_s & 0 & 0 & +k_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k_s & 0 & 0 & +k_s \\ -k_n & 0 & 0 & k_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & +k_s & 0 & 0 & -k_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & +k_s & 0 & 0 & -k_s \end{bmatrix}$$

where k_n , k_s are the compression stiffness coefficient and the lateral stiffness, respectively. Sliding occurs when $\mu F_n = |F_s|$. The lateral stiffness becomes zero. Contact element stiffness matrix can thus be written as [5]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} k_n & 0 & 0 & -k_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -k_n & 0 & 0 & k_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

COMPACTING SIMULATION

Vacuum Bag Structure

In reality, the fiber preform is first produced by the textile process. Then the successive layers of fabric nest randomly. After fabrics were flattened and possibly border stitched to avoid yarn shifting, the fabric layers are pressed by a vacuum bagging process. The entrapped air is removed before resin is injected. During the vacuum bagging process, air compression is not directly applied to the fabrics. Instead, it is applied to the vacuum bag. The vacuum bag compresses the fabric layers through contact. The vacuum bag is a thin heat-resistant flexible sheet. Furthermore, a porous release cloth and a few layers of bleeder papers are often placed between the fabric stacks and vacuum bag. Since we are only interested in the pressure applied to the fabric and not the vacuum bag itself, we can model the vacuum bag as a simplified net structure that has a resemblance to a fishing net, as shown in Figure 2. All neighboring rod elements are connected by a frictionless pin. The stiffness matrix of each rod element is similar to one of the multi-chain elements. The contact element is only established where a net node \mathbf{n}_0 contacts fiber node \mathbf{m}_1 physically. The total internal tensile force at each node is obtained by examining all connected rod elements. External force \mathbf{p}_c is applied to each node evenly to mimic the air compression. By setting the net element with soft material properties, the net structure represents a flexible vacuum bag. Otherwise, the net structure can be treated as a rigid mold if the material properties are set as a hard material, such as steel.

Residual nodal force is the sum of internal and external nodal forces. External nodal force \mathbf{p}_c is predefined; internal nodal force will be calculated in each step. Refer to Figure 2. Elements $\mathbf{n}_1\mathbf{n}_0$, $\mathbf{n}_0\mathbf{n}_2$, $\mathbf{n}_3\mathbf{n}_0$, and $\mathbf{n}_0\mathbf{n}_4$ are four neighboring elements in the net structure connected by node \mathbf{n}_0 . The node \mathbf{m}_1 is on the fiber digital chain. A contact element $\mathbf{n}_0\mathbf{m}_1$ is inserted between \mathbf{n}_0 and \mathbf{m}_1 . Tensile forces \mathbf{f}_1 , \mathbf{f}_2 , \mathbf{f}_3 , and \mathbf{f}_4 are calculated from displacement of elements and applied to the node \mathbf{n}_0 separately. They can be derived as:

$$\mathbf{f}_i = \mathbf{K}_i \Delta \mathbf{L}_i; \quad i=1 \sim 4,$$

where \mathbf{K}_i is the stiffness of digital element i and $\Delta \mathbf{L}_i$ is displacement. The contact force \mathbf{f}_c between net structure and fiber chain is also calculated as:

$$\mathbf{f}_c = \mathbf{K}_n \Delta \mathbf{L}_c,$$

where K_n is the compression stiffness of yarns and ΔL_c is displacement of the contact element. The sliding force between fibers and net element is calculated and added into the stiffness matrix using the same equations presented in the digital element method. Since we are only interested in applying the compacting force on the fabric and not the deformation of the net structure, some degrees of freedom in the net nodes can be constrained. For example, the net nodes can only move along the direction of the external compacting force. Figure 3 shows simulation of the vacuum bag compression.

Randomly Nested Layers

2-D woven and braided fabrics are by far the most commonly used textile preforms for composite applications. The 2-D woven structure is characterized by the interlacing warp and weft, while braided fabrics are formed by the intertwining of yarns with each other. The thickness of the textile structure is often achieved by nesting 2-D preforms layer by layer. Therefore, there is no guarantee that each layer will nest exactly the same way. They will nest randomly. The investigation on deformation of fabric induced by shifted layers has been conducted. The evidence from the simulation results has shown some new deformations induced by the stacking force.

Numerical Results

A larger scale numerical simulation of the textile process and compacting process was conducted at AFRL. First, a single digital layer, which consists of 24 braider yarns and 6 axial yarns, was generated based upon parameters obtained from a triaxial braid specimen. Each yarn was then discretized to 19 digital chains for representing a bundle of fibers inside a yarn. Further, a single compacted layer was achieved after applying the multi-chain digital element approach. By cutting off the edges to limit the boundary influence, we were able to obtain the fabric architecture of a single compacted layer. We shifted and nested five duplicated digital layers to match the specimen. The upper mold and bottom mold were modeled as two net structures with rigid material properties. Compressing force was distributed to all the nodes on the upper net structure evenly. The bottom net structure was fully constrained. The edges of all layers were constrained in a way to prevent the shrinkage of fabric and allow further compacting in the thickness direction. Each digital layer has 70,878 nodes. The total number of equations for this case was more than 350 k. The initial thickness of the digital model was 4.20 mm. Numerical simulation of compression was continued until the thickness reached the experimental measurement, which was 3 mm. The compression force was increased gradually during the simulation to avoid large deformation due to possible ill-conditioned stiffness matrix. A comparison of experiment and digital simulation is shown in Figure 4. The results show excellent agreement between experiment and digital simulation. The multi-chain digital element with integrated net structure approach represents a significant improvement of the description of realistic fiber architecture over the previous uncompact description.

Surface Reconstruction

The geometry is crucial to mechanical analysis of textile composites. The multi-chain digital element approach with integrated vacuum bag structure is able to predict the realistic fiber architecture. The reinforced material properties are determined by fiber locations, sizes, and orientations. However, the fiber is generally too small an entity for efficient modeling. In a typical single yarn, there are as many as 1-24 k fibers.

Geometrical modeling of the textile composite is usually done at the yarn level. The yarn is treated as a solid entity, which consists of two materials: fibers and resin. The yarn geometry was defined as a sequence of cross sections along the yarn path. Each cross section is a polygon, which consists of a sequence of vertices. This representation of yarn morphology can reflect the mechanical properties of high modulus along the yarn path. The physical properties of the yarn can be simply set by orienting the cross section of the yarn binormal to the center line. A yarn-smoothing method was implemented into the software to approximate the yarn geometry [12].

Multi-cluster Method

BSAM (B-Spline Analysis Method) is a computational structural analysis code developed by the University of Dayton Research Institute for the AFRL. It is a B-spline-based analysis tool for composite materials research [13]. To be used in BSAM, the polygon-based textile geometry needs to be converted into B-spline parametric volume. An arbitrary coordinate transformation in 3-D space can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3), & y &= y(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3), & z &= z(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3); \\ 0 &\leq \xi_1 \leq 1, & 0 &\leq \xi_2 \leq 1, & 0 &\leq \xi_3 \leq 1; \end{aligned}$$

and represented by parametric spline approximation as [14]

$$X(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) = \sum_{i=0}^{N+1} \sum_{j=0}^{M+1} \sum_{k=0}^{P+1} N_i(\xi_1) N_j(\xi_2) N_k(\xi_3) C_{ijk} \quad . \quad 1)$$

The $(N+2)(M+2)(P+2)$ volume coefficients C_{ijk} , also called volume control points, were obtained by using a collocation method. The number of shape functions in each direction corresponds to the order of spline. Quadratic B-spline is used below. It could be very difficult to obtain C_{ijk} by solving equation 1) directly. However, we can compute C_{ijk} sequentially by performing surface approximations of cross section contours.

Therefore, points in the B-spline surface can be written as

$$X(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) = \sum_{i=0}^{N+1} \sum_{j=0}^{M+1} N_{i,p}(\xi_2) N_{j,q}(\xi_3) C_{ij}(\xi_1) \quad 2)$$

where the direction of ξ_1 is conveniently aligned with the fiber direction. Thus for a sequence of cross sections of constant ξ_1 , we compute a table of $C_{ij}(\xi_1)$ coefficients. For each function $C_{ij}(\xi_1)$, we perform one-dimensional approximation of the ξ_1 coordinate dependence and obtain the 3-D approximation coefficients C_{ijk} .

Each cluster represents a set of parametric coordinates (ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3) , $0 \leq \xi_1 \leq 1$, $0 \leq \xi_2 \leq 1$, and $0 \leq \xi_3 \leq 1$. A single-cluster model is the simplest way to define the tow geometry. However, it could miss detailed sharp corners of yarns. Also it could produce some Jacobian errors due to the degenerate elements. A multi-cluster model was developed to represent a solid entity with several connected sub-volumes. First, the volume was divided into several sub-volumes, each sub-volume was then converted to the parametric volume using the above method. The connected surfaces shared the same set

of control points. The multi-cluster method is able to preserve the sharp corners, and improve the quality of tow geometry. Figure 5 shows a 4-cluster solid geometry.

Experimental Validating

To understand of the importance of morphology accuracy, two digitally simulated tow geometries were used in BSAM analysis. The results were compared with a Moiré interferometry, which was an experimental method to evaluate the redistribution of strain in composites due to release of residual stresses. The first geometry was the top layer of an uncompacted five-layer, triaxially-braided composite. The second one was the same top layer after being numerically compacted. The fiber tow cross sections of the uncompacted geometry have much more rounded shapes than those of the compacted and those of the experimental. The compacted geometry also produces much smaller gaps between the fiber tows in the in-plane view which is in good agreement with the experimental observations.

The application of the Moiré grating requires surface preparation, which resulted in the removal of excess resin from the surface of the composite and a slight reduction of the fiber tow thickness of the surface tows. Therefore, an additional morphology with virtual “sanded” surface was created, which is clearly more representative of the actual morphology. Thus three numerical results are compared to experiment, namely 1) uncompacted tows, 2) compacted tows, and 3) compacted “sanded” tows. The BSAM predictions obtained with the uncompacted geometry yield quite smeared values of the strain component, while the compacted and compacted “sanded” geometries yield, in most cases, remarkably good agreement with the experimental data.

CONCLUSION

A multi-chain digital element with integrated vacuum bag structure approach was developed for modeling the realistic compacted fiber tow architecture of a multilayered 2-D triaxial braided fabric. A multi-cluster method was developed to obtain the solid model from the digital simulation. The compacted geometry yielded excellent agreement with experimental data.

Figure 1. Digital element

Figure 2. Vacuum bag structure

Figure 3. Vacuum bag compression

Figure 4. Numerical results and experimental observation

Figure 5. 4-cluster solid geometry

Figure 6. In-plane strain variation along the cut

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the Air Force Research Laboratory under Contract FA8650-05-D5052 with the University of Dayton Research Institute.

References

1. Cox, B. and Flanagan, G., "Handbook of Analytical Methods for Textile Composites," NASA Contractor Report 4750, March 1997.
2. Bogdanovich, A. and Pastore, C., "Mechanics of Textile and Laminated Composites," 1st ed., Chapman & Hall, New York, 1996.
3. McBride, T. and Chen, J., "Unit-Cell Geometry in Plain-Weave Fabric during Shear Deformation," Composites Science and Technology, Vol. 57, 1987, pp. 345-351.
4. Kim, H. and Swan, C., "Algorithms of Automated Meshing and Unit Cell Analysis of Periodic Composites with Hierarchical Tri-quadratic Tetrahedral Elements," Int. J. for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 58, 2003, pp. 1683-1711.

5. Sihn, S., Iarve, E. and Roy, A., "Three-Dimensional Stress Analysis of Textile Composite, Part 1. Numerical Analysis," *Int. J. Solids Structure*, Vol. 41, 2004, pp. 1377-1393.
6. Lomov, S., Huysmans, G., Luo, Y., Parnas, R., Prodormou, A., Verpost, I. and Phelan, F., "Textile Composite Modeling Strategies," *Composite: Part A*, Vol. 32, 2001, pp. 1379-1394.
7. Zhou, G, Sun, X. and Wang, Y., "Multi-Chain Digital Element Analysis in Textile Mechanics," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 64, 2004, pp. 239-244.
8. Zhou, E., Mollenhauer, D. and Iarve, E., "Image Reconstruction Based Modeling of 3D Textile Composite," *AIAA SDM*, 2007, Waikiki, Hawaii.
9. Faessel, M., Delisee, C., Bos, F. and Castera, P., "3D Modeling of Random Cellulosic Fibrous Networks Based on X-ray Tomography and Image Analysis," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 65, 2005, pp. 1931-1940.
10. Wang, Y. and Sun, X., "Digital-Element Simulation of Textile Processes," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 61, 2001, pp. 311-319.
11. Miao, Y., Zhou, E., Wang, Y. and Chessemann, B., "Mechanics of Textile Composites: Micro-geometry," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, 2008, pp. 1671-1678.
12. Sihn, S, Wang, Y., Zhou, E. and Roy, A., "Computational Modeling of 3D Textile Composites," *ICCM15*, June, 2005, Durban, South Africa.
13. Iarve, E., "Mesh Independent Modeling of Cracks by Using Higher Order Shape Functions," *Int. J. for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 56, 2003, pp. 869-882.
14. Piegl, L. and Tiller, W., "The NURBS Book," 2nd ed., Springer, New York, 1997.